

The noted author, writer, professor, and philosopher, [Aaron Afilalo](#), specializes in international trade law, business transactions, and contracts.

He began his career in law serving as a clerk of Paul J. Liacos who was the Chief Justice of the Supreme Judicial Court of Massachusetts.

His scholar topics of interest included the treatment of intellectual property in free trade areas, the European Union's system of judicial remedies, the international rules for the protection of cross-border investment and the law governing the elimination of non-tariff barriers to trade.

Afilalo was practicing cross-border commercial and financial transactions between Europe and the United States and many other cases related to intellectual property matters in the New York City. At the same time, was also a part of Suffolk Law School in Boston.

While serving as the adjunct professor, he taught courses in intellectual property and international trade.

Furthermore, Afilalo was affiliated with the Harvard Law School, where he served as legal writing instructor.

At the present moment, he serves as a professor of Law at [the Camden faculty at Rutgers](#).

Afilalo holds a Bachelor's degree in Political Science from the Harvard University, a J.D. (magna cum laude) in Law from the Boston University School of Law, and a LL.M. in International Law from Harvard Law School.

Over the course of his career he has [authored and co-authored a number of publications](#) and books.